

ISSUES OF ATTRACTING NEW UZBEKISTAN RESIDENTS TO CULTURAL AND PUBLIC ENTERTAINMENT INSTITUTIONS

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***Abstract.** This article talks about public, cultural and entertainment institutions operating in our republic and their characteristics. Also, suggestions and recommendations will be given with particular attention to the issue of attracting people to public viewing institutions, which is one of the urgent tasks of today, and increasing the number of viewers.*

***Keywords:** public performance institutions, cultural managers, arts organizations, advertising, analytical debate, seating arrangement, idea, funding, performance.*

Since time immemorial, our people have paid great attention to parades, public performances, and entertaining holidays. It can be said that holding social, political or religious holidays on a large scale as a national celebration has become a unique tradition. Public viewing institutions serve as a place of special importance in uniting the people, realizing a noble idea, and conveying the essence of state policy. First, let's answer the question of what public performances are. A public performance is a stage production created for a public performance with the participation of 100 or more people on a specific occasion. These are entertainment or political, cultural, social events organized for theatrical performances - performances, shows, circus performances, concert programs, holidays and elections. Currently, there are several genres that have been approved in the practice of public performances. They are as follows:

- Public theatrical performance;
- Public theatrical concert;
- Literary-artistic musical compositions;
- Memorial ceremony performances;
- Public sports shows;
- Performances held in water and ice;
- Carnivals;
- Folk performances

The required place for them to be held is public viewing institutions. Concert halls, open-air amphitheatres, ice palaces such as "Khumo Arena", some shopping malls with their own "stage" that are widely recognized as public entertainment institutions are making a good profit from entertainment events today, while state theaters whose main task is to share enlightenment with the people, cultural centers, concert halls and other institutions are not even able to cover themselves due to lack of audience. As managers of culture, it's a mistake, in my opinion, to ignore it.. As Michael M. Kaiser points out, "Almost every arts organization begins as an audience's dream." Indeed, there is an art that should have an audience - a demon. One of the biggest problems today is the lack of viewers. But it's not the viewer's fault. Attracting the audience was considered the task of the works created by artists in all periods. It will be appropriate to carry out a number of analytical works on attracting the population to them. First of all, it is necessary to conduct business using marketing methods in accordance with the laws of the market. Peter Drucker, one of the great representatives of the field of marketing, says: "The way a company thinks about its products is not the most important condition for the future of the business or its success. What the consumer thinks about the purchase, what they see as the value of the purchase, determines the nature, direction and

chances of success of the business." In fact, we are living in a time when the rapid increase in production and the emergence of many types of goods make it difficult for an entrepreneur to sell his product. This phenomenon is happening in any field related to people and the market, and it certainly does not exclude art. We can consider this simply in the example of theaters. Because theaters are the heart of society in many ways.

1. Use of advertising. This method, which cannot be understood in one way, can reach a very wide audience. Television, social networks, billboards, and radio broadcasts can be used for advertising. On the one hand, it seems that this process itself requires money. But considering the fact that theater actors are in many ways well-known people and have thousands of followers on social networks, it will not be a very difficult process, in my opinion. No matter how good your performance is, today's demand is good advertising! The view that "in the last century it was possible to gather a large audience without advertising" is no longer enough. Because the advertising industry was not so developed in the last century. If you have the opportunity to go to see a great work, the best advertisement will surely win. Sometimes I hear experts in the field say: "We don't have enough quality viewers," they say. Creating a high-level audience is actually the task of industry experts. If the universities do not produce high-level specialists, we complain about the audience whose field is completely different! Being able to pay attention is actually a virtue. But today we see very negative ways of attracting attention among many people. Use of PR (especially black PR), opening 18+ topics, spreading false sensational information has unfortunately become a tradition.

2. Analytical debates. For the development of the industry, its specialists must act responsibly. In this regard, it is necessary to organize debates and podcasts for staged performances (let's say other performances as well). Although this may seem like a "time-consuming" exercise, the results of it are estimated differently on the Internet, and you can tell by watching enough films that are

mostly mentioned as having a lot of mistakes and flaws. Any show that gets mentioned - recognized (whether it's bad or good) is something that deserves attention. I see a lot on the social pages of famous bloggers:

- they tell their good and bad impressions about the books they read,
- they criticize the films they have seen.
- pre-host podcasts and analytical debates about their various projects, concert programs and performances.

This is an undeniably effective method.

3. Giving a name to the seating scheme. Attracting people to theaters using modern marketing methods is one of the most popular methods abroad. Why should you not buy a ticket for a special seat in the theater with your loved one's name on it? I think it's a great idea and it depends on the skills of the theater team to organize it with extras. I will add another interesting idea. You can also help raise funds by decorating the theater's wardrobe as an open museum and stocking it with different characters' clothes for those who want to take photos wearing the clothes. Ideas based on creativity like the above are the demand of today, and surprising people remains the most interesting and, in turn, the most difficult task. Although such methods are few, I think they will have a positive effect on the activities of public viewing institutions. Today, the promptness required by the times does not bypass the sphere of culture and art. Especially as the global funding landscape is changing so rapidly, cultural and arts organizations and public performance institutions are also increasingly concerned about how to proceed. Of course, in this regard, managers of cultural and arts institutions have the ability to have a range of leadership styles, develop organizational stability through effective management, achieve revenue streams through entrepreneurship, have fundraising strategies for their organization, and of course offer better value to their target audience. should be. This process is a special path and it is not easy to follow. Any

manager who works in the field of culture and art, trying to reach a wider audience and establish strong partnerships in concert halls, museums, galleries, theaters, art palaces, cultural and recreational parks and cultural centers, and to create a sustainable organization or institution. should fully understand the concept of fundraising and gain practical skills in this regard. This is an English word (fundraising), which in traditional usage means "money collected for a specific purpose, especially for charity." In business terms, this word refers to the process of receiving money from investors to invest in specific companies, projects, etc.

As a formula for attracting more people to public viewing institutions in Uzbekistan, we can cite the following 7 step-by-step road maps.

1. Idea. This stage requires only ideal and creative thinking, foresight, and conclusions drawn from sufficient experiences. A common saying among marketers and businessmen. Idea is expensive. A good idea means good money.

2. Funding. This stage can also be achieved by selling ideas. But the best way for an idea to remain personal and to ensure its continuity is to be able to convince others of the idea. There are a lot of entrepreneurs in the world who love art and are not afraid to spend money, and if you convince them, you can get a good amount of money for your cause. This will definitely come from the hands of people who know and follow the rules of perfect cooperation.

3. High-quality work. You have your own idea. You also got money through it. The task now is to create a quality work using the funds wisely. At this stage, you are required to be a master of your work, in addition to qualities such as a creative thinker, an entrepreneur, and a persuasive person. Because the only thing that reaches the audience and attracts the audience to you is your creative product.

4. Funding. If you've done the previous steps enough to get enough of your ledger in place, it's natural that you'll need more funds. Because now you have to advertise, and it's natural that these advertising methods are not cheap either.

5. Advertising. Part of the money raised is best spent on advertising. This is actually the rule of the day. Without good advertising, it is very difficult to reach your desired audience. Moreover, we see that this method increases the purchasing power of even low-quality products today.

6. Demonstration. Now the audience you have been waiting for is with you and it is at this stage that they will come back and even become a source of profit for you.

7. Profit. Any art that has achieved an audience, enough funding, and notoriety has not always found a way to make a profit everywhere. The last step is profit, and you will get profit when you follow the above six steps correctly. The next step will not be in this sequence. Especially if you don't have money problems. Because now you have viewers and sponsors who believe in you.

Bibliography

1. Haydarov A. Madaniyat va san'at sohasini boshqarish asoslari. – Toshkent: Kamalak. 2019. – 192p.
2. Qosimova D. Menejment nazariyasi. . – Toshkent, Tafakkur-bo'stoni. 2011. 336p
3. Nabiyev E., Raximova D., Mavloniy SH., Zamonaviy menejment nazariyasi va amaliyoti. –Toshkent: Akademiya, 2006. 252 p
4. Boboxo'jayev A. Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida natijaga yo'naltirilgan budjetlashtirish menejmenti – Toshkent: Lesson Press. 196p.
5. Haydarov A. Ijodiy faoliyatni rejalashtirish va boshqarish. – Toshkent: Kamalak. 2019. 81p– 192 p

6. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Madaniyat vazirligining madaniyat va san’at sohasining jamiyat hayotidagi o‘rni va ta’sirini yanada oshirish borasida olib borgan ishlari yuzasidan hisobotidan. Manba: Vazirlikning 2021-yil uchun hisoboti. – Toshkent: 2022.

7. Ma’rufov Z. O‘zbek tilining izohli lug'ati. 1-jild. I A –R. Moskva. Rus tili nashri. 1981. 632.

8. Najmetdinova M. Ommaviy-madaniy tadbirlarning o‘ziga xos xususiyatlari// jur. “Science and innovation” xalqaro ilmiy jurnali: №1. 2022 yil – 948 b. (892-902). – Toshkent.: <http://scientists.uz/uploads/journal/202201.pdf>

9. Alimasov V., Manzarov Yu. O‘zbekistonda ma’naviy-ma’rifiy soha: nazariya va amaliyot (falsafiy-sotsiologik tadqiqot). Navro‘z. Toshkent 2014. 120 p.